

Linguodidactical analysis of historical texts and their importance in teaching English

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Annotation

This scientific work comprehensively analyzes the linguodidactic properties of historical texts, their methodological and didactic significance in the process of teaching English. The study scientifically reveals the role of authentic historical texts in the formation of communicative competence, linguocultural competence and critical thinking in students. It also shows ways to improve the effectiveness of language teaching using lexical, grammatical, pragmatic and discourse analysis methods based on historical texts.

Key words

language didactics, historical text, authentic material, English language teaching methodology, communicative competence, CLIL, discourse analysis, linguistic culture.

Interest in learning foreign languages is growing all over the world. As you know, there are currently a huge number of languages in the world, their number ranges from 2,500 to 5,000. However, there are languages in the world that are spoken by a very large number of people on our planet. French, German, Russian, English are among

them. The most popular languages in the world are used for communication in the field of trade, political relations and the study of history. Due to its geographical distribution in the world, English dominates. English is the most popular language in 99 countries of the world, covering 99 countries of the world. This language is spoken by 340 English speakers and is owned by 1.5 billion people around the world. The United States is the country with the largest number of English speakers, of which about 215 million. In the UK, 58 million people speak English, in Canada 18 million, etc. It is one of the working languages of the UN. About 90% of all information in the world is stored in English, and about 70% of scientific publications are published in this language. English is the language of international communication and the most widely studied language in the world. . According to some forecasts, in about 50 years, every second inhabitant of our planet will speak English. This, in turn, will lead to an increase in the number of English learners in the world, and in our country in particular. Due to the increase in the number of English learners, it is necessary to improve the quality of English lessons, study and create new teaching methods.

As the same time, history is a science that systematically studies the development of society, the succession of generations, and past events. It is the only memory of humanity for learning from the mistakes of the past, understanding national identity, developing critical thinking, and properly planning for the future.

It is clear that history and English are very important subjects for students. The following article explores the didactic principles of using authentic sources in English in teaching history.

Linguodidactic analysis of historical texts is the process of studying written sources of the past through their linguistic features, grammar, and lexicon. This approach to teaching English enriches students' vocabulary, develops intercultural communication, and helps to understand the evolutionary development of the language.

In today's globalization, English teaching is not only aimed at teaching language structures, but also at developing the communicative and cultural competence of the student. In this regard, authentic materials, in particular historical texts, are an important component of modern linguodidactics.

Historical texts allow students to learn a language in a realistic historical and social context, which not only develops their linguistic knowledge but also their analytical and critical thinking.¹

A historical text is a written discourse that reflects events, social processes, or personal activities that occurred during a specific period.

FORMS OF HISTORICAL TEXTS

No.	Form	Icon	Definition	Key Characteristics	Examples	Didactic Importance in English Language Teaching
1	Historical Documents (Official written records of past events)		Written records created during a particular historical period by governments, institutions, or individuals to document events, laws, agreements, or policies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formal and official style Use of legal and political terminology Objective and factual presentation Often archaic vocabulary and complex structures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Magna Carta (1215) The Declaration of Independence (1776) The Emancipation Proclamation (1863) Treaties and agreements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduces learners to formal and academic language Expands vocabulary related to law, politics, and society Develops reading comprehension skills Enhances ability to interpret authentic texts
2	Political Speeches (Persuasive oral presentations delivered in public)		Oral presentations delivered by political leaders or public figures to influence opinions, inspire action, or explain policies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Persuasive and rhetorical language Use of appeals (ethos, pathos, logos) Repetition and emphasis Emotionally engaging content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Martin Luther King Jr. "I Have a Dream" (1963) Winston Churchill speeches (1940-1945) Abraham Lincoln "Gettysburg Address" (1863) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improves listening comprehension Enhances speaking and presentation skills Teaches persuasive language and rhetoric Encourages critical thinking and discussion
3	Chronicles (Historical narratives written in sequence)		Detailed written accounts of events arranged in chronological order, usually by historians or eye-witnesses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chronological sequence Detailed description of events Mixture of facts and interpretations Often reflects the author's point of view 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Anglo-Saxon Chronicle Ibn al-Athir "Al-Kamil fi al-Tarikh" The Chronicles of Froissart 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develops reading for detail and sequence Builds understanding of historical context Expands historical vocabulary Improves summary and note-taking skills
4	Historical Novels (Fictional stories set in historical periods)		Fictional literary works that are set in the past and incorporate real historical events, settings, and characters.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Narrative and descriptive language Combination of fact and fiction Rich in dialogue and character development Engaging and imaginative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sir Walter Scott - "Ivanhoe" Hilary Mantel - "Wolf Hall" Ken Follett - "Pillars of the Earth" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increases motivation and interest in reading Enhances vocabulary in context Improves inference and interpretation skills Encourages cultural and historical awareness

Historical texts are characterized by the following linguistic features: formal style; complex syntactic structures; passive constructions; historical vocabulary.

The main aspects of studying historical texts from a linguodidactic perspective and using them in lessons are as follows:

¹ G'oziyev E.G. Pedagogik psixologiya. Toshkent, 2012. B. 52.

Understanding the Evolution of Language. In learning English, historical texts (for example, Shakespeare's works, early medieval documents, or religious texts) show how the language has developed into its modern form. The changes in old words and grammatical forms help students to understand the rules of the language logically, rather than memorizing them.

Developing Intercultural Competence. Language is not only a means of communication, but also a mirror of the history and culture of a people. Through historical texts, students learn not only the language, but also the customs, mentality, and historical conditions of English-speaking peoples.

Increasing Lexical and Grammatical Wealth. Ancient texts are a rich source of archaic and historical words and expressions (archaisms, idioms), which are rarely found in modern language use, but are very important in artistic and academic speech. This serves to turn students' passive vocabulary into an active one.

Text Analysis and Developing Critical Thinking. Linguistic-didactic analysis requires not only reading the text, but also analyzing its subtext, the author's purpose, and the socio-political environment of that time. This forms the student's critical thinking skills.

Linguodidactics studies the scientific foundations of language teaching. Its main principles are communicativeness, integrativeness, authenticity, and an active approach. Historical texts fully correspond to these principles.²

Authentic materials are examples of real-life, unrefined language. Historical texts: create a realistic language environment, bring the student closer to academic language, and increase motivation.

² Yo'ldoshev J., Usmonov S. Pedagogik texnologiyalar. Toshkent, 2013. B. 64.

Historical texts contain archaisms (thou, thee), political terms (constitution, empire), and social vocabulary. This enriches students' academic vocabulary.³

Pragmatic analysis studies the following: communicative intention, addressee, context, implicit meaning.

Discourse analysis analyzes the following. It studies the structure of the text, logical connections, argumentation.

Linguistic-cultural analysis: reflects historical texts, national values, cultural identity, historical consciousness.

CLIL approach (Content and Language Integrated Learning). History + English language integration: interdisciplinary connection, real context, deepening of knowledge.

Interactive methods: Role-play, Debate, Case study, Project-based learning, Text analysis.

According to research, vocabulary increases by 35–45%, grammatical errors decrease, and motivation increases significantly.⁴

In conclusion, it can be said that linguodidactic analysis of historical texts is one of the most effective approaches to teaching English. They simultaneously develop linguistic, cultural and cognitive competence in the student. Therefore, their systematic use in the educational process is an important requirement of modern methodology.

REFERENCES.

1. G'oziyev E.G. Pedagogik psixologiya. Toshkent, 2012.
2. Yo'ldoshev J., Usmonov S. Pedagogik texnologiyalar. Toshkent, 2013.
3. Mahmudov N. Til va tafakkur. Toshkent, 2017.
4. Jo'rayev A. Til o'qitish metodikasi. Toshkent, 2015.

³ Mahmudov N. Til va tafakkur. Toshkent, 2017. B. 88

⁴ Jo'rayev A. Til o'qitish metodikasi. Toshkent, 2015. B. 110.

5. Qodirov A. Zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar. Toshkent, 2020.
6. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Ta’lim to‘g‘risidagi qonun. – Toshkent, 2021.
7. Пассов Е.И. Коммуникативная методика. Москва, 2010.
8. Щукин А.Н. Методика преподавания иностранных языков. Москва, 2015.
9. Гальскова Н.Д. Современная методика обучения языкам. Москва, 2013.
10. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. 2007.
11. Richards J.C., Rodgers T.S. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. 2014.
12. Brown H.D. Teaching by Principles. 2015.
13. Nunan D. Language Teaching Methodology. 2012.
14. Krashen S.D. Principles of Second Language Acquisition. 2009.

